

FIGURE 7

Fig. 7 Length evolution of the first molars of *Eucricetodon* in the localities Mazan (MP21), Hoogbutsel (MP21), Olalla 4A (MP21/22) and Montalban 1D (MP23). Comparative measurements are taken from Freudenthal (1996). All measurements are in mm.

FIGURE 8

Fig. 8 Size distribution (length vs. width) of the lower (m) and upper (M) molars of *Eucricetodon* from Mazan compared to *E. atavoides* and *E. nanoides* from Olalla 4A (Spain), and *E. atavus*, *E. sp.1* and *E. sp.2* from Hoogbutsel (Belgium). Comparative measurements are taken from Freudenthal (1988, 1996).